

NEXT TENSE IN UZBEK, RUSSIAN AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Abstract.

In this article, the comparison of the verb word category in Uzbek, Russian and Karakalpak languages, the next tense form of the verb, similarities and differences were studied.

Keywords: verb word category, next tense, tense, base, consonant, vowel, affix, pure next tense, present-next tense, next tense suspect verb.

Verb-the richest in grammatical categories in all 3 languages, grammatical nature is the most complex category. Words belonging to the verb word category indicate the process.

The action, state meaning of a verb is expressed through its special grammatical categories. The verb has grammatical categories like rank – zalog – da'reje, mile – naklonenie – meyil, tense – Vremya – Ma'ha'l, person and son – liso I chislo – bet Ha'm san in all 3 languages.

The verb stands out among all word categories in terms of its versatility in meaning, its richness in grammatical categories, forms, as well as its most important place in the composition of the sentence. The Russian linguist academician Peshkovsky was certainly right when he said: "when word categories are compared to planets, the verb is the sun among them." The use of the verb as a central clause in Uzbek also proves this¹.

In Uzbek, the Pure future tense form is made with the affix-Ajax (- yjak). The affix is derived from the Khwarezmian dialect of the literary language, which is not widely used in modern Uzbek literary language. For example: we will work in our collective farm after graduation. Bathers are like those who will always live in the memory of the people². In Uzbek in general, the next Tense is a syntactic phenomenon, and the present-next tense form of the verb is expressed in context, depending on the circumstances, or generality in the tense, or the next tense. For example: my father works at school. Like my mother will stay on duty in the hospital tomorrow.

And in Russian there are 2 forms of the next tense. From the completed verb type, a simple form of the next Tense is made, and from the unfinished verb type, a complex form of the next Tense is made. The simple form of the next Tense is toned down to resemble the form of the present tense. For example: next tense: ya Ido, Ti idyash, an(A) idyat. Now a simple form of the next time: ya poydu, Ti poydyosh, on(a) poydyot. The complex form of the next Tense is made by using the auxiliary verb bit attached to the infinitive form of the leading verb. In such a complex form, only the bit part is toned, and the leading verb always comes in the form of an infinitive. For example: ya budu rabotat, Ti Budesh chitat, on(a) budet igrat.

¹ Muhiddinova X va boshqalar. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. Toshkent. 2006. – B. 110.

² Azizov O. va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi Toshkent, 1965. – B. 65.

In Karakalpak, verbs in the next tense form indicate work-actions that will be worked on next time, before the process of speaking. Verbs in the next tense form in Karakalpak are spiritually divided into the following types³. 1. The meaning of the present-next Tense is understood by the tusked forms of the case verbs in the form-a,-e, - y together with the person-number affixes. These verb forms come in terms of meaning and structure, corresponding to the present and future tenses. 2. Suspect next tense-in this tense, it is not clear whether the work-action will work or not, it is said in the sense of suspicion. This meaning is understood through the split -ar/-er, -r and non -split-mas/ - mes forms of the next tense. 3. The exact next Tense is the meaning of the tense -A, -e, -Y+is expressed through the conjugation of the person-number affix bila of the adjective in the jaq form. For example: like oqiyjaqpan, barajaqpan, oynayjaqpan. 4. The purposeful next Tense is the meaning of the tense -which is understood through the forms of the target mile in the maqshi/-mekshi form that are toned down by the person-number affixes. For example: like kelmekshimen, kelmekshisen', kelmekshi.

The forms of the next tense in Uzbek are studied as follows. 1. Strict future tense form it can also be called a definite future tense. This form is formed by the affix-Ajax, - yjak. For example: I will go, like I will work. 2. The next Tense is made with the suspect Form -(A)R affix. For example: I will go, I will go, I will read. 3. The next Tense is formed by the necessary form-digan affix. For example: like going, coming, going. 4. The next Tense is made with the target form -moqchi affix. For example: like I want to leave, I want to go, I want to sit.

The present-next tense form of verbs (glagoli dvizheniya), which in Russian means walking movement, in Uzbek and Karakalpak languages often gives the meaning of the next tense. For example: I go - satellite - ketemen, like kelaman - pridu - kelemen. the next tense form, made with the suffix-Ajax (- yjak), represents the next tense which is strictly present. The meaning of the Russian language is given by the simple form of inflected verbs in the next tense. The next tense present in Uzbek and Karakalpak is given by the use of the verb suspect with the verb in the next tense form of vozmojno, mojet bit, to give such a meaning in Russian. For example: Yozarman - может быть я напишу - jazarman - maybe I'll write , yozarsan - может быть ты напишешь - jazarsan' - maybe you'll write, yozar - может быть он(а) напишет - jazar - maybe he will write.

The affixes of simple Future Tense and complex future tense forms in Russian are the same, o are distinguished from each other by type and meaning. In Karakalpak, however, the affixes of the definite past tense and definite future tense are similar but in the past tense, the affix is added directly to the verb base, and in the next tense, the case is added after the affix - a,- e,- y of the verb. Also, although the general meaning of the past verb tense in languages is close to each other, there are quite a few differences between them. Past tense forms have more and different additional meanings in Uzbek and Karakalpak languages.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth noting that in conclusion, we must say that the Present Tense has several meanings and types of meanings in every 3 languages. Strictly next tense, next Tense is a form of suspicion, next Tense is a form of purpose, next Tense is a form of purpose; and in Russian there is a simple form of the next tense from the completed verb type, and a complex form of the next tense from the unfinished verb type, and in Karakalpak language there are such types as the present-next tense, The forms of the past tense are more

³ Da'wletov A va boshqalar. Ha'zirgi qaraqalpaq a'debiy tili. - No'kis, 2010. - B. 169.

numerous than in Russian, and in Uzbek and Karakalpak languages it is necessary to use in additional words in Russian to mean these meanings of the past tense. To do this, it is necessary to study each language more deeply and diligently.

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